

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ Creating $-EE + pp = -m_0c^2$ Through Changes in Space and Time?

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$x=vt$ is a simple spacetime relation linked to physical motion in Newtonian mechanics, special relativity and even quantum mechanics (we argue). $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, the quantum free particle wavefunction (complex probability we argue) contains the spacetime relation $-Et+px$ which is a Lorentz invariant. A Lorentz invariant, however, is a mathematical object which begs the question: Why is it manifest physically in space and time through $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$? We suggest here that this spacetime function changes in such a way (measured by d/dx and d/dt) such that a quadratic use of these operators (because $-Et+px$ is quadratic) yields the associated Lorentz invariant $-EE + p \cdot p c^2 = -m_0c^2$. At the same time, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is consistent with equal weights to all x,t points implied by $x=vt$. In other words, nature seems to manifest the spacetime Lorentz invariant such that it naturally creates the second key Lorentz invariant $-EE+ppc^2$ (1-dimension) without contradicting probabilistic features of $x=vt$ (equal x,t weights).

Special Relativity

We first note that Newton's kinetic energy $.5m_0v^2$ may be obtained without knowing $F=dp/dt$ or the full form of special relativity. We consider a rest mass m_0 , which represents inertia, a physical property. If seen from a frame moving with $-v$, the m_0 mass moves. One may suggest that its inertia may possibly increase via:

$$m(v) \rightarrow E = m(v)c^2 + f(v) \text{ such that } f(v=0)=0 \quad ((1a))$$

One may also note that one sees $m(v)c^2+f(v)$ moving with v and define a function:

$$p = (m_0 + f(v))v \quad (\text{we set } c=1) \quad ((1b))$$

One may ask: How do the two quantities in the moving frame relate to each other to first order in $f(v)$? One may create various relations, but one may see that p contains an extra v and is a vector and so one would like to create a scalar using p and link it to E . The simplest scalar is $p \cdot p$ (without introducing an arbitrary vector). Then, to first order:

$$m_0c^2 + f + 2m_0fv = m_0c^2 + p^2 = m_0c^2 + m_0^2v^2 + 2m_0fv$$

$$f(v) \text{ for } v \rightarrow 0 \text{ is tiny so } 2m_0fv = m_0^2v^2 \text{ (highest order term) so}$$

$$f = .5m_0v^2 \quad ((2))$$

Thus, one may obtain Newton's kinetic energy without any notion of $F=dp/dt \rightarrow m \int v dv = \int F dx$ or a full solution of special relativity with $1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$.

We note that we considered $m_0 + f(v)$ and picked highest order terms, but $m_0 + f(v)$ may be considered to be a full expression (i.e. $f(v)$ represents a full power series in v of some function). If one considers this function to be $g(v)$, then:

$$g(v)g(v) m_0 m_0 = m_0 m_0 v v g(v)g(v) + m_0 m_0 \quad \text{or } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((3))$$

Furthermore, if one arbitrarily considers the math function $-Et+px$ (without knowing that it is a Lorentz invariant) then:

$$-Et+px = - (m_0 + f) t + (m_0 + f) vx = t(m_0 + f) (-1+vv) \quad ((4))$$

It is known that $m_0 + f = m_0 cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and so if $t = t_1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ one has an invariance equation just like $-EE + ppcc = -m_0 m_0 cc$. This suggests that both:

$$-Et+px \quad \text{and} \quad -EE+ppcc \quad ((5))$$

are Lorentz invariants. Now, one may argue that the notion of a Lorentz invariant is simply a mathematical one, but we suggest that nature not only manifests the spacetime equation $x=vt$, but also the spacetime Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ in such a way that the change of a function of $-Et+px$ in space and time (measured by the usual d/dx , d/dt translation in space and time operators) creates the second Lorentz invariant $-EE+ppcc$. In other words, the free particle quantum wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a physical manifestation of one Lorentz invariant creating another without violating probabilistic features of $x=vt$.

$-Et+px$ Creating $-EE+ppcc$

$x=vt$ is a spacetime function associated with constant motion in space (with $x=0$, $t=0$ as initial points). $-E+px$ is a math function in spacetime, but that does not mean a priori that it has any particular meaning associated with a physical particle. We argue, however, that mathematically one may create a function of $-Et+px$, such that the natural operators measuring changes of this function, d/dx and d/dt , in fact create the second Lorentz invariant $-EE+ppcc$.

One may create such a function as

$$\exp(-Et+px) \quad \text{such that } d/dx \text{ partial yields } p \exp(-Et+px) \text{ and } d/dt \text{ partial, } E \exp(-Et+px) \quad ((5))$$

Alternatively, one may create an imaginary math function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ ((6))

One might ask: Which should one choose? We first wish to demonstrate that both functions allow for the second Lorentz invariant $-EE+ppcc$ to be created via space and time changes of either $\exp(-Et+px)$ or $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In the first case, one uses d/dx and d/dt and the second, $-id/dx$ partial and id/dt partial to create:

$$-EE+ppcc \quad \text{via} \quad -d/dt \text{ } d/dt + d/dx \text{ } d/dx \quad ((7))$$

The reason that one uses a quadratic form of the operators is that $-Et+px$ is a quadratic expression as well.

This does not answer, however, whether one should choose $\exp(-Et+px)$ or $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. We argue that the latter must be chosen to be consistent with

$$x=vt \quad ((8))$$

((8)) suggests equal weights at different x and t points and so this fundamental physical idea should be maintained, but $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ demonstrates changes in x,t (keeping $\exp(-iEt+ipx)\exp(iEt-ipx)=1$) via d/dx and d/dt partial which creates the second Lorentz invariant

$$-EE+ppcc \quad ((9))$$

when one uses d/dt d/dt and d/dx d/dx (quadratic form because $-Et+px$ is quadratic).

Physically, one has two intertwined spacetime equations $x=vt$, which is used to define the notion of velocity which then gives rise to the definitions of $E=mvcc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ through the principle of special relativity, but also to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which maintains $x=vt$ (equal t,x weights) through $\exp(-iEt+ipx)\exp(iEt-ipx)$, but physically creates, through specific physical changes in space and time (measured by d/dx partial, d/dt partial) the Lorentz invariant $-EE+ppcc$. As $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is written as a math function in spacetime, quadratic use of d/dt d/dt partial and d/dx d/dx partial creates $-EE+ppcc$. Even without using d/dt and d/dx explicitly, changes in x and t go as p and E multiplied by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. We argue that the notion of Lorentz invariants in special relativity is not simply a mathematical one, but one that is manifested physically, giving rise to the free particle quantum wavefunction (without spin) $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Newtonian mechanics uses one spacetime equation for a free particle, namely $x=vt$. This formula is used when establishing special relativity, but special relativity yields two key invariants $-EE+ppcc$ and $-Et+px$ (1-dimension). The second is a spacetime equation. One might argue that Lorentz invariants are math objects from linear algebra and do not have much physical relevance. We suggest, however, that one may create a math function in x,t whose natural changes in x,t (measured by d/dt partial, d/dx partial) create the second Lorentz invariant $-EE+ppcc$. In addition, this math function may be shown to be compatible with the spacetime equation $x=vt$ which gives every x,t point equal weight. This suggests that this function is linked with probability. The function in question is $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. One may see that it contains one Lorentz invariant, but that its d/dt partial and d/dx partial results (taken twice because $-Et+px$ is quadratic in variables) creates the Lorentz invariant $-EE+ppcc$ via its changes in spacetime. Its modulus of 1 is consistent with all x,t having equal weight. Thus, nature seems to manifest both the space time equation $x=vt$ and $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, such that it creates $-EE+ppcc$ through its changes in x,t and is consistent with $x=vt$.